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Научная статья

ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ ЦИФРОВОГО МАРКЕТИНГА НА РЫНКЕ АВТОЗАПЧАСТЕЙ

DIGITAL MARKETING TECHNIQUES FOR THE AUTOPARTS MARKET

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В статье рассмотрены цифровые инструменты, позволяющие автомобильным компаниям увеличить присутствие в онлайн-пространстве и привлечь клиентов через поисковые системы, социальные сети и другие каналы. Проблема заключается в недостаточном внимании российских компаний к цифровому каналу сбыта через сеть Интернет в условиях, когда большинство населения страны увеличивают присутствие в интернет-среде для различных целей. Это может привести к неэффективному использованию ресурсов компании и снижению отдачи от инвестиций. Интегрированный подход к digital-маркетингу позволяет разработать единую согласованную стратегию, объединяющую все аспекты цифровой коммуникации. В условиях повышенной конкуренции и высоких ожиданий покупателей инструменты цифрового маркетинга могут значительно увеличить клиентскую базу данных, оптимизировать расходы и повысить рентабельность.

The article discusses digital tools that allow car companies to increase their presence in the online space and attract customers through search engines, social networks and other channels. The problem lies in the insufficient attention of Russian companies to the digital sales channel via the Internet in an environment where the majority of the country's population is increasing their online presence for various purposes. This can lead to inefficient use of the company's resources and lower return on investment. An integrated approach to digital marketing allows us to develop a single coherent strategy that combines all aspects of digital communication. In an environment of increased competition and high customer expectations, digital marketing tools can significantly increase the customer database, optimize costs, and increase profitability.

Ключевые слова: *маркетинг в социальных сетях, поисковая оптимизация, управление репутацией в поисковых системах, электронный маркетинг, искусственный интеллект, аналитические инструменты, таргетированная реклама, контекстуальная реклама.*

Key words: *social media marketing, search engine optimization, search engine reputation management, email marketing, artificial intelligence, analytical techniques, targeted advertising, contextual advertising.*

Introduction.

The relevance of digital marketing tools implementation is determined by the current state of the domestic market [2; 21]. Demographics who are simultaneously potential customers tend to spend the majority of personal time online searching for opportunities to satisfy their individual needs, fulfill work duties and for other miscellaneous reasons. Similar high-level expectations are true for product choice in competitive markets, such as in the market of autoparts. Therefore, businesses and companies are striving to meet customer needs through increasing online presence exponentially [7]. Practically, they regularly develop and introduce advanced digital marketing technologies, — which seems to be a fundamental strategy for conducting business these days [11].

Enhanced competition due to a constantly increasing number of market participants is considered to be a growing concern for companies which aspire to stand out and become prominent market players among other competitors [22]. It is becoming challenging to stay salient and noticeable retaining and attracting new customers. With this regard, digital marketing tools are indispensable for goods promotion and expanding customer base. Unless companies pay due attention to social networks and other media, the rate of return on marketing investment will most probably result in a financial loss and profits are highly likely to plummet [13]. Digital marketing tools serve not only as analytical means but also as effective methods of overcoming crisis situations and as anti-crisis measures.

Perfectionism is a strategy that enables companies to strive for improving performance and exceeding business outcome «by means of introducing a Kaizen management system, selecting methods and techniques aimed at maximum satisfaction of customer needs and adding value» [16, p. 296]. Though perfectionism is viewed as a negative personal quality in psychology, marketing companies expect perfectionism as a key social position of job applicants which resonates with their own strategy — excellent performance results, aspiration to develop high-quality marketing materials, scrupulousness and attention to detail which contributes to enhanced brand perception [5; 19–20].

The aim of this paper is to consider a marketing strategy of online presence maximization through the mix of marketing tools in a competitive media environment. The strategy implies expanded audience reach, precise targeting, accumulating vast information about personal customer details [3], active attraction of consumer attention and engaging them with brands, virtually ubiquitous presence in every corner of the world, the opportunity to manage brand perception. The correlation between the pull and push strategies is constantly regulated by growing customer needs which are becoming more sophisticated under the influence of the advanced range of goods and services on the market. On the other hand, the push strategy is also on the rise, due to multiple communication channels which provide opportunities for companies to promote goods and services.

The scientific novelty lies in the comprehensive analysis of marketing techniques as manifestations of perfectionism in professional promotional activity under the circumstances of elevated competition. Businesses are striving to enhance the image of their brands as much as possible, underlining their significant achievements and performance results, which is conveyed in reporting documents: “Perfectionism in annual reports accentuates needs and interests of the target audience — high quality products, social well-being, including customers, investors, stakeholders, employees, and citizens of presence regions” [15, p. 84].

The practical value of this analysis lies in the fact that digital marketing tools have to be in focus at the very early stages of professional education [6; 14; 17]. As intangible resources, they serve as intellectual capital in any company which can be relied on and utilized as a competitive advantage being developed by highly trained and qualified professionals. From the practical standpoint, turning the attention to digital marketing has certain substantiation. Firstly, transferring the right of selecting products to the consumer side, enhancing the share of personalized marketing as a means of brand and client communication based on customer needs, interests, and preferences [8].

Secondly, decentralization of information supplier implies distribution of decision-making and control to multiple individuals within a network [10]. Thirdly, transmission of multi-media content involves delivering different data types in the form of image, video, sound and text, which function in combination owing to the combination of advanced digital methods such as data compression, adaptation, streaming, which allow for constant content updates [4].

Results.

1. *Contextual and Targeted Advertising*. Such advertisements appear or pop-up in a search engine in response to a search by keywords, matching the topic of those words. Contextual advertising is broadcast only to the audience that needs it. The digital technique is called targeted advertising which relies on restricting audience settings, selecting the right channels and, therefore, finding suitable potential customers who are further exposed to the targeted advertising. The basic targeting parameters are the following:

- a) demographics (aimed at nationality, social status, gender, age, education, income level, employment);
- b) psychographic (consumer values, personality type, social position, opinion, lifestyle, interests and preferences);
- c) behavioral (those reflected in the browser history, purchase history and other recent user activity on websites);
- d) time-based (in accordance with the hours or days of the week during which the sale of goods or services is possible, for example, relevant for the catering industry);
- e) geographical (applies to people who are in a certain area during a certain period of time or who live in a specific locality).

2. *Search Engine Optimization (SEO)* involves working on a website and optimizing it internally, in accordance with search engine recommendations. The goal is to increase a website's visibility in search engines. This tool is an important component of a marketing strategy, because setting up a company's website properly will help rank it highly among competitors. SEO focuses on internal website factors. Promotion methods include the following: creating interesting and useful content for visitors; user-friendly navigation and a well-thought-out menu; optimizing meta-tags, titles, and website text; internal linking; improving website loading speed; troubleshooting technical issues on the website.

3. *Social Media Marketing (SMM)*. The advantage of this tool is its relatively low cost and high efficiency. The development trends for this tool should be attributed to the messaging niche. A platform like TELEGRAM is a vivid example. This messenger is rapidly developing in today's environment, which also provides an opportunity to implement this technique quite effectively. There are numerous ways to promote your product, for instance, creating business chat-bots, running your own channel, Telegram-ads, among others. Currently, regular domestic users spend most of their time on the following services: video, social media, messaging apps, and games. Simultaneously, the popularization of social networks and other services leads to the fact that the role of Internet advertising is constantly growing, demonstrating an annual increase [12]. Therefore, integration of SMM into a company policy is a good solution for developing a marketing strategy.

4. *Email Marketing* is a system of sending emails to users' email addresses in order to stimulate sales and maintain customer loyalty for a particular company's product or service. Email-marketing remains one of the most effective channels due to its personalized communication and high return on investment. From a marketing perspective, email marketing is a way of communication with clients on a personal basis, allowing for the development of long-term, trust-based relationships. The primary purpose of an email is to attract consumers' attention, obtain feedback, or encourage them to purchase a product or service [1]. Email marketing, as a form of digital advertising, is considered a powerful marketing channel, surpassing other options. Its primary benefit is di-

rect communication which allows for the opportunity to inform existing and potential consumers about important company events and, if necessary, communicate directly with consumers.

5. *Artificial Intelligence (AI)*. Among the latest trends, it is worth noting that the use of AI is one of the most modern tools for optimizing advertising campaigns and personalized user experience. With AI support, online advertising is becoming a cutting-edge technology in the marketing field. AI offers personalized, unique, and original solutions. AI can play a crucial role in improving the measurement and optimization of advertising campaigns. By analyzing performance data, AI can help formulate the right strategy and identify which aspects of marketing strategy are working and which need improvement. AI can also be used to improve the selection of meta-tags for SEO-optimization, improve data selection for targeted advertising, and generate video and photo content, text. However, it's important to remember that this tool is still in development, and it's necessary to verify and validate the data.

6. *Analytical techniques*. The shift of communication with consumers to digital channels has exposed new opportunities for researching and analyzing their behavior. There are a number of services that provide analytics in the digital environment.

A. *Yandex.Metrica* offers a wide range of capabilities for analyzing website traffic, traffic sources, time spent on the site, and other data. These tools are the foundation for analytics in Russia, and many prefer this service.

B. *Webvisor* is a service from Yandex that records user actions on a website and allows company representatives to see it through their eyes.

C. *Serpstat* analyzes a company's website and its competitors, providing a detailed report. It examines ads used in contextual promotion and obtain an SEO report with an analysis of the semantics and keywords for which competitors outperform the company's website.

D. *Online Market Intelligence* helps conduct a variety of research, from testing creative ideas and hypotheses to assessing the impact of content and advertising messages on target audiences. It is useful for shaping brand image and online communications.

E. *Mediascope*, a technology-based research company and leader in the Russian media research and advertising in the media monitoring market, which offers a powerful tool for analyzing and monitoring advertising and media, and measures internet users or monthly internet audiences.

The Russian auto part market is demonstrating a rapid trend of increasing its volume. A current trend in the auto parts market is shifting purchasing formats. A large number of sales have moved online; hence, the structure of supply channels is changing. Operators like Ozon and Wildberries have their own well-developed logistics and offer convenience for consumers. To promote an auto parts store, it's important to use both traditional methods and digital marketing. Digital marketing is more effective at comparable costs, as it allows for attracting more customers. Sales statistics shows a steady increase in the share of sales through online stores and aggregators. The current digital marketing tools in the auto parts market embrace:

a) *SEO and contextual advertising* for an auto parts store website allow for optimization of a store's website for user search queries, which helps attract more traffic from search engines, such as Yandex and Google that use algorithms based on neural networks difficult to predict. It is necessary to compose a semantic core of key phrases, i.e. distribute them into high, medium and low frequency bands. Specifically for the auto parts trade, the semantic core would be the following words: *auto parts, car parts, auto parts, auto products, spare parts to order, original parts from the manufacturer, parts replacement, parts delivery, parts catalog*. These words and phrases help cover a wide range of user queries and increase the visibility of a website or store in search engines.

b) *Catalogs on the website and interaction with social networks* — placing auto parts catalogs on the website, allowing users to quickly find the parts they need and make purchases without any extra effort. Social media engagement engage audiences across social platforms, share promotions and special offers, and derive customer feedback. For an online store website, one can use the

"Availability Catalog" module, which automatically generates a catalog from the remaining product and link it to the user's vehicle. It sets up targeted advertising and increases the likelihood of conversion.

c) *Promotion through aggregators.* Collaboration with auto parts aggregators promote store's products on popular marketplaces, where users can compare prices and close beneficial deals.

d) *Affiliate programs for auto parts stores.* There are a number of different ways to promote your store using affiliate programs. One such method is to attract new customers using the "refer a friend and get a discount (or a percentage for sale)" approach. This is implemented through a referral or promo code system. To enable this, implementation of a corresponding feature on a website is required.

e) *SEO, targeted advertising, and contextual advertising.* Continuous analysis and optimization of existing marketing techniques allows companies to improve their effectiveness, identify strengths and weaknesses, as well as adjust their promotion strategy to achieve higher profits.

f) *Search engine reputation management (SERM).* The main purpose of this technique is to manage mentions of a company or brand. It includes handling negative feedback, categorized as natural, provocative, and targeted. Dealing with each type of negative feedback is different and requires a different set of methods. The effectiveness of dealing with online negative feedback directly depends on the speed of response from the company's reputation management team. For the auto parts market, this is a crucial component of the online segment. Factually, most users pay attention to product reviews, and in the modern environment, this can be a decisive factor in making a purchase, even overbidding the price. The ease of online opinion exchange increases the importance of handling objections in sales.

g) *Improving customer-focused website design and content.* In addition to SEO optimization of a site, it is necessary to pay attention to its design and usability. The website needs to be optimized for all devices a user might have: PC, smartphone, or tablet. The website's design, user-friendly buttons, and clear functionality can help retain customers and prevent them from opting for a rival company. Content requires constant updating. It is important to keep users informed about what is happening in the company and what they are striving for to achieve. This contributes to stronger, trust-based relationships.

h) *Company history.* A section dedicated to the company's history, values, mission, vision, and achievements helps users better understand the brand and create a stronger connection with the company.

i) *Price list,* a separate section with a detailed list of prices for the company's products or services, which allows customers to quickly review prices and choose the most suitable option.

j) *Contact information.* Having a separate page or block on each page with the company's contact information, including address, phone numbers, email, and links to social networks.

Conclusion.

To conclude, the perfectionist strategy for digital marketing techniques serves for reaching a global audience, increasing chances of sales through a personalized approach, and reducing marketing costs. A variety of digital tools helps quickly expand the target audience. Due to economic growth, the Russian auto parts market is characterized by a high level of imports and significant demand, including non-original and used parts. A wide choice of vehicles and autoparts leads to perfectionistic tendencies among car owners who are searching for high automobile performance and flawless appearance. All the digital marketing techniques described above prove their efficiency. Integrating these tools, taking into account their most effective interaction, forms a robust and sustainable digital marketing strategy for an auto business. Through the implementation of the digital techniques, companies are able to conduct a detailed analysis of their marketing strategy and make the necessary adjustments to achieve better profitability and return on investment. Notewor-

thily, users are increasingly shifting to aggregators and website orders, – which necessitates devoting as much, if not more, attention to online sales. Developing a targeted strategy, high-quality content, and using a variety of techniques are key components of a successful digital marketing campaign in the auto parts market.

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